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**FINANCIAL LEVERAGE AND PROFITABILITY A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF
STEEL AUTHORITY OF INDIA LIMITED AND TATA STEEL LIMITED**

*** DR. P. SANJEEVI**

ABSTRACT:

In this paper, an attempt has been made to identify the impact between Financial Leverage and Profitability of the SAIL and TSL, taking into consideration the level of these two steel companies Financial Performance and also investigates the relationship between the financial advantage and the earning per share. In addition, it aims to describe how the earning capacity of the firm is influenced by the financial charges. In the present study, an attempt also has been made to explain the relationship between the Financial Leverage and Profitability (Earning per share and market price per share) and how effectively the firm is able to debt financing. The study was based on secondary data collected from annual reports of SAIL and TSL for the study period i.e. 2003-04 to 2012-13. Ratio analysis, t-test, Correlation Analysis and Financial Leverage Analysis has been used to analyze the data. The study suggests the company should maintain optimum level of financial leverage it is affecting the profitability.

KEY WORDS: Capital Structure, Financial Leverages, Profitability Earning per Share and Market Price per Share.

INTRODUCTION:

Business solvency is the ability of an entity to pay its debts with available cash. Solvency can also be described as the ability of a firm to meet its long-term fixed expenses and to accomplish long term expansion and growth. For the real growth of the company the financial manager should plan an optimum capital for the company. The optimum capital structure is one that maximizes the market value of the firm. In practice, capital structure planning means selecting a desired debt-equity combination in advance. While planning the capital structure of a firm, the following important factors have to be considered: 1. Financial Leverage 2. Operating Leverage 3. EBIT-EPS Analysis 4. Cash Flow Analysis 5. Cost of Capital. Let us understand capital structure planning is depends upon its firms leverage. In this study, an attempt is made to analyze the financial leverage and profitability of the two leading steel companies in India. An application of researched solvency management practices would definitely help this sector to perform with better profitability.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

Main objectives of the Paper is as follows

- To study and analyze the financial Leverage of Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited.
- To identify impact of profitability on financial Leverage of Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES:

For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis is to be tested:

- H₁:** There is no significant difference between Leverages (Operating, Financial and Combined) and Earnings per Share.
- H₂:** There is no significant difference between Leverages (Operating, Financial and Combined) and Market Price per Share.

METHODOLOGY:

The design of the present study is descriptive and analytical in nature and covers the period of 10 years from 2003 to 2013. The data which is required for the analysis and that could fulfill our objectives has been collected mainly from two sources, viz 1) primary and 2) secondary data.

Primary data was collected from the officials and other employees through interviews and discussions regarding different financial aspects of the SAIL and TSL.

The study is also based on the secondary data obtained from the audited balance sheets and profit & loss accounts and also the annual reports of SAIL and TSL. Besides, the facts, figures and findings advanced in similar earlier studies and the government publications are also used to supplement the secondary data.

For assessing the behavior of data statistical techniques have been used such as descriptive, correlation, t-test, skewness, and kurtosis are used for this study. For these statistical measures are calculated by using SPSS soft ware

PROFILE OF STEEL AUTHORITY OF INDIA LIMITED:

Steel Authority of India Limited (SAIL) is engaged in the business of manufacturing and marketing steel and its allied products. It is a fully integrated iron and steel maker, producing both basic and special steel products for construction, engineering, power, railway, automotive and defense industries and for sale in export markets. SAIL is also among the five Maharatnas of the country's Central Public Sector Enterprises. The company primarily operates in India and is headquartered in New Delhi, India. The Government of India owns about 86 percent of SAIL's equity and retains voting control of the Company.

The Steel Authority of India Limited (SAIL) is a company registered under the Indian Companies Act, 1956 and is an enterprise of the Government of India. It has five integrated steel plants at Bhilai (Chhattisgarh), Rourkela (Orissa), Durgapur (West Bengal), Bokaro (Jharkhand) and Burnpur (West Bengal). SAIL has three special alloy steels plants viz., Alloy Steels Plant at Durgapur (West Bengal), Salem Steel Plant at Salem (Tamil Nadu) and Visveswaraya Iron and Steel Plant at Bhadravati (Karnataka).

SAIL's wide ranges of long and flat steel products are having much demand in the domestic as well as in the international market. This vital responsibility is carried out by SAIL's own Central Marketing Organization (CMO) that transacts business through its network of 37 Branch Sales Offices spread across the four regions. 25

Departmental Warehouses, 42 Consignment Agents and 27 Customer Contact Offices. CMO's domestic marketing effort is supplemented by its ever widening network of rural dealers, who meet the demands of the smallest customers in the remote corners of the country. With the total number of dealers over 2000, SAIL's wide market spread ensures availability of quality steel in virtually all the districts of the country. SAIL's International Trade Division (ITD), in New Delhi - an ISO 9001:2000 accredited unit of CMO, undertakes exports of Mild Steel products and Pig Iron from SAIL's five integrated steel plants. With technical and managerial expertise and know-how in steel making gained over four decades, SAIL's Consultancy Division (SAILCON) at New Delhi offers services and consultancy to clients world-wide. Division (GD) and SAIL Safety Organization (SSO) allocated are located at Kolkata.

PROFILE OF TATA STEEL LIMITED:

Tata Steel Ltd is the world's 10th largest steel company and the world's 2nd most geographically diversified steel producer. The company is a diversified steel producer with major operations in India, Europe and South East Asia. They have manufacturing units in 26 countries and at present in 50 European and Asian markets. The company together with their subsidiaries, engages in the manufacturing and sale of steel products in India and internationally. They offer hot and cold rolled coils and sheets, galvanized sheets, tubes, wire rods, construction rubbers and bearings. The company also involves in prospecting, discovering and mining iron ore, coal, Ferro alloys, and other minerals; designing and manufacturing plants and equipment for steel, oil and natural gas, energy and power, mining, railways, ports, aviation, and space industries; and agricultural implements. Further, they offer alumina, dolomite, and monolithic refractories, as well as silica refractories for coke ovens and the glass industry, manufactures bricks, sponge iron lumps and fines; and rolls for applications in integrated steel plants, power plants, and government mint, as well as paper, textile and food processing sectors.

Tata Steel's operations are grouped under six Strategic Business Units include Bearings Division, Ferro Alloys and Minerals Division, Agrico Division, Tata Growth Shop (TGS), Tubes Division and Wire Division. They have introduced several brand steel products, including Tata Steelium (the world's first branded Cold Rolled Steel), Tata Shaktree (Galvanized Corrugated Sheets), Tata Tiscon (rubbers), Tata Pipes, Tata Bearings, Tata Structural, Tata Agrico (hand tools and implements) and Tata Winma (galvanized wire products) Tata Steel Ltd was incorporated in the year 1907 with the name Tata Iron & Steel Company Ltd. In the year 1911, the company commenced the operations of the first Blast Furnace or the 'A' Blast Furnace. In December 2, 1911, the first collieries were obtained and the first cast of pig iron was produced. In the year 1912, the first ingot of steel rolled out of the Sakchi Plant. In October 1912, the Bar Mills started their commercial production. Also, the 'B' Blast Furnace became operational during that year. In the year 1918, India's first steel (coke) plant was established in Jamshedpur. In the year 1925, the New Rail Mill, Merchant Mill and Sheet Mill went into operation. In the year 1931, they opened an apprentice shop. In the year 1941, they started manufacture of special steel for war purpose. They

produced a wide variety of special steels required for defense purposes including armored cars called 'Tatanagars'. In the year 1943, Howrah Bridge was constructed from steel supplied by the company

THEORETICAL VIEW OF LEVERAGE:

The term leverage, in general, refers to the relationship between two interrelated variables. In financial matters, one financial variable influences another variable. Those financial variables may be cost, sales revenue, earnings before interest and tax (EBIT), output, earnings per share, etc. In the leverage analysis, the emphasis is on the measurement of the relationship of the two variables, rather than on measuring the variables.

Leverage has been defined as, the action of a lever and mathematical advantage gained by it. In other words, leverage allows accomplishing certain things that are otherwise not possible. The concept is valid in business also. From the financial management point of view, the term leverage is commonly used to describe the firm's ability to use fixed cost assets or sources of funds to magnify the returns to its owners.

According to James Home, leverage is, "the employment of an asset or sources of funds for which the firm has to pay a fixed cost return". Here fixed cost (operating cost) or fixed returns (financial cost) remains constant irrespective of the level of output.

The leverage associated with investment (asset acquisition) activities is referred to as operating leverage, while leverage associated with financing activities is called financial leverage and combination of both is composite leverage. While we are basically concerned with financial leverage for purpose capital structure decision of the firm, the discussion of operating leverage is to serve as a background to the understanding of financial leverage because the two types of leverage are closely related. Leverages are discussed below:-

(a) **Operating Leverage:** - Operating leverage refers to the use of fixed cost in the operation of a firm. A firm will not have operating leverage, if its ratio of fixed costs to total costs is nil. For such a firm given change in sales would produce the same percentage in the operating profit or earnings before interest and taxes.

$$\text{Operating Leverage} = \frac{\text{Contribution}}{\text{EBIT}}$$

(b) **Financial Leverage:** Financial leverage is also known as trading on equity. It is defined as the ability of a firm to use fixed financial charges to magnify the effects of changes in EBIT on the earnings per share i.e., preference share capital and debt capital including debentures with fixed rate of interest. These fixed financing costs provide the same magnification effect on the firm's earning per share (EPS), that operating leverage has on firm's EBIT.

$$\text{Financial Leverage} = \frac{\text{EBT}}{\text{EBT} - \text{Contribution}}$$

(c) **Combined Leverages:** - When the financial leverage is combined with operating leverages, the result is referred to as total or combined leverage. Operating risk (fixed) is measured by operating leverage and financial risk is measured by financial leverages.

$$\text{Combined Leverage} = \frac{\text{EBT}}{\text{Contribution}}$$

The following table shows various combinations of operating and financial leverage and their combined effect.

Table: Combination of Leverage Effect

Operating Leverage	Financial Leverage	Combined Effect
High	High	This combination is very dangerous policy, which should be avoided.
Low	Low	This combination is a very cautious policy and not assuming risk.
High	Low	This combination have adverse effect of operating leverage were taken care of by having low financial leverage.
Low	High	This combination is an ideal situation, The company can follow aggressive debt policy.

Leverage Analysis: An attempt is made to analyze the leverage ratios. It refers to the ability of a firm in employing long term funds having a fixed cost to enhance returns for the owners. But a higher leverage obviously implies higher outside borrowings and it is hence riskier. If the business activity of the firm suddenly takes a dip. But a low leverage does not having borrowed funds at a fixed cost to earn higher profits. Therefore, we try to study the leverages of SAIL, and TSL, and to know the profitability of the above companies. The leverage analyses are presented in Table- 2

Table 2. Statement of Leverage Ratios

Year	SAIL			TSL		
	Operating Leverage	Financial Leverage	Combined Leverage	Operating Leverage	Financial Leverage	Combined Leverage
2005-06	1.44	1.23	1.27	1.28	1.26	1.26
2004-05	1.11	1.46	1.28	1.28	1.28	1.28
2005-06	1.20	1.26	1.26	1.27	1.26	1.26
2006-07	1.12	1.24	1.24	1.28	1.26	1.28
2007-08	1.11	1.22	1.23	1.26	1.22	1.22
2008-09	1.12	1.22	1.16	1.26	1.16	1.16
2009-10	1.12	1.24	1.18	1.26	1.18	1.18
2010-11	1.19	1.27	1.27	1.26	1.18	1.18
2011-12	1.24	1.16	1.21	1.22	1.17	1.20
2012-13	0.95	1.15	1.14	1.26	1.15	1.26
Mean	1.15	1.24	1.15	1.11	1.17	1.15
SD	0.12	0.045	0.13	0.12	0.045	0.13
Standard Deviation	1.23	1.14	1.25	1.24	1.14	1.24
Kurtosis	1.16	0.37	1.2	1.17	1.2	1.2

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL, and TSL from 2003-04 to 2012-13.

Figure: 1

Figure: 2

It can be seen from Table 2, reveals the leverages performance of SAIL for the 2003-04 to 2012-13. It can be seen that the Operating Leverage showed in fluctuating trend. Minimum leverage was seen in the year 2012-13 at 0.99 times and maximum leverage was at 1.44 times in the year 2003-04. Average operating leverage for the last 10 years was seen at 1.15 times. On comparison TSL: highest and lowest of operating leverage was seen at 1.50 times in the year 2012-13 and 0.95 times in the year 2011-12. Average operating ratio was found i.e.1.11 times. TSL has higher standard deviation. For Skewness results, SAIL and TSL are positively skewed. For kurtosis values, TSL follows platykurtic pattern and SAIL follows leptokurtic pattern, i.e. the values are more peaked than the other company. Overall the analyses, the result this ratio is exhibited in Figure-1&2.

Financial Leverage is concerned, SAIL and TSL showed in fluctuating trend. This leverage for SAIL, minimum leverage was in the year 2007-08 at 1.02 times and maximum leverage was at 1.23 times in the year 2002-03. Average financial leverage for the last 10 years was seen at 1.09 times. On the other hand TSL, highest and lowest of financial leverage was seen at 1.24 times in the year 20012-13 and 1.02 times in the year 2005-06. Average operating ratio was found i.e.1.12 times. TSL has higher Standard deviation. For Skewness both companies are positively skewed. For kurtosis values, SAIL follows platykurtic pattern and TSL follows leptokurtic pattern, i.e. the values are more peaked than the other company. From the above analyses, the result of this ratio is exhibited in Figure-1&2.

For combined leverage for SAIL and TSL showed fluctuating trend. It is observed that minimum leverage in the year 2007-08 at 1.13 times and maximum leverage was at 1.77 times in the year 2003-04. Average combined leverage for the last 10 years operating leverage was seen at 1.25 times for SAIL. On the other hand TSL, highest and lowest of year 2007-08. Average combined ratio was found i.e.1.25 times. For standard deviation, SAIL has higher value. Skewness results of this ratio, both companies are

positively skewed. For kurtosis values showed that both companies follows platykurtic pattern. For the analyses, the result this ratio is exhibited in Figure-1&2.

Table: 3 - Statement of Earnings per Share and Market Price per Share

Year	SAIL		TSL	
	EPS	MPS	EPS	MPS
2003-04	6.08	32	47.29	575.05
2004-05	16.5	63	62.75	400.97
2005-06	9.72	83	63.33	536.41
2006-07	15.02	113	58.01	399.68
2007-08	18.25	185	7.55	78.37
2008-09	14.94	96	8.39	24.92
2009-10	16.35	253	56.87	597.14
2010-11	11.87	170	75.63	620.17
2011-12	8.6	115	67.84	470.13
2012-13	5.2	128	50.28	312.24
Mean	17.25	124	49.79	401.5
S.D	6.41	4.64	23.49	209.05
Skewness	-0.35	0.73	-1.26	-0.94
Kurtosis	-1.43	0.54	0.49	-0.215

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL from 2003-04 to 2012-13.

From the table No. 2 it is found that EPS for SAIL and TSL showed in fluctuating. It is a good measure of profitability. EPS is a small variation of return on equity capital and is calculated by dividing the net profit after tax divided by the total number of equity shares. It can be seen that SAIL has maintained maximum EPS in the year 2007-08, i.e. Rs. 18.25 and minimum was in the year 2012-13 i.e. Rs. 5.2 and average mean value of this ratio was Rs. 17.25 and the standard deviation was Rs.6.41. On the other hand, the same ratio compared to the TSL, maximum EPS was seen in the year 2010-11 at Rs. 75.63 and minimum in the year 2007-08 was Rs. 7.55 times and average EPS was found i.e. Rs. 49.79. For standard deviation TSL has high when compared to the SAIL. For skewness both the companies are negatively skewed. For the result of Kurtosis; TSL is platykurtic pattern and SAIL follows leptokurtic pattern, i.e. the values are more peaked than the other company. For the analysis, the result of this ratio is exhibited in Figure-3.

From Table -3 it is clear that Market price per share for SAIL and TSL showed fluctuating trend. It is found that SAIL has lower MPS in the year 2003-04 at Rs.32 and Higher was Rs.253 in the year 2009-10 and average MPS for the last 10 years was seen

at Rs.124. On the other hand TSL highest and lowest of MFS was seen at Rs. 644.17 and Rs.24.92 in the year 2008-09. Average of this ratio was Rs.402 for the year 2009-10 and Rs.24.92 in the year 2008-09. For Standard deviation TSL has higher value. For Skewness for the last 10 years. For Standard deviation TSL negatively skewed. For Kurtosis, SAIL follows a platykurtic pattern and TSL shows leptokurtic pattern. i.e. the values are more peaked than the other company. For the analysis, the results this ratio are exhibited in Figure-3

COMPARATIVE STATUS OF MFS AND EPS

Figure (a)

Figure (b)

Source: Compiled from Annual Reports of SAIL and TSL from 2001-02 to 2010-11

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS (LEVERAGES AND PROFITABILITY WITH EPS AND MFS)

Hypotheses are tested to know the relationship strength in between leverage and profitability. Given hypothesis examines the relationship between leverage and earnings per share and the relationship between leverage and Market price per share. Further each hypothesis includes three sub-hypotheses are tested by using correlation coefficient for to know the relationship strength and t- test used for hypothesis result. The simplest formula for computing t-value to test significance of a correlation coefficient employs the t-distribution:

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{N-2}{1-r^2}}$$

The degrees of freedom for entering the t-distribution is $N - 2$. Table value of (10-2) i.e. 8 degrees of freedom at 1% or 5% level of significance is 3.35 or 2.306 for two tailed test.

TEST OF SIGNIFICANCE (USING EARNINGS PER SHARE):

Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference between Operating Leverage and Earnings per Share.

Table: 4 - Correlation and t-test result for Operating Leverage and Earnings per Share

Company	r value	Correlation result	t value	Hypothesis result
SAIL	-0.21	Negative	/0.61/	Accepted and insignificant
TSL	0.228	Positive	/0.66/	Accepted and insignificant

Source: Computed.

Inference: Table 6 reveals that the correlations between the Operating Leverage and Earnings per Share for SAIL has negative and TSL has positive relationship. Whose co-efficient determinations for SAIL and TSL are 0.0441 and 0.0519 respectively. That is 4.41% and 5.19% of variance in the operating leverage is accounted by earnings per share for each the company. For t-test result it is clear that the computed value is less than critical value for SAIL and TSL. Where, the null hypothesis is accepted and insignificant for both SAIL and TSL. Further, it is found that relationship between operating leverage and earnings per share can be weak at 5% level of significance.

Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference between Financial Leverage and Earnings per Share.

Table 5 - Correlation and t-test result for Financial Leverage and Earnings per Share

Company	r ² value	Correlation result	t' value	Hypothesis result
SAIL	-0.89	Negative	/5.53/	Rejected significant and
TSL	-0.15	Negative	/0.43/	Accepted insignificant and

Source: Computed.

Inference: Table 6 reveals that the correlation between the Financial Leverage and Earnings per Share for SAIL and TSL have negative. The co-efficient determinations of SAIL and TSL are 0.7921 and 0.0225 respectively. That is 79.21% and 2.25% of variance in the financial leverage is accounted by earnings per share for both the companies. For t-test result, it is clear that the computed value is less than critical value for SAIL and TSL. Where, the null hypothesis is rejected for SAIL and accepted for TSL, but insignificant for both SAIL and TSL. Further, it is found that relationship between financial leverage and earnings per share can be strong and negative for SAIL. Whereas, TSL has weak and negative relationship at 5% level of significance.

Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference between Combined Leverage and Earnings per Share.

Table 6 - Correlation and t-test result for Combined Leverage and Earnings per Share

Company	r ² value	Correlation result	t' value	Hypothesis result
SAIL	-0.53	Negative	/1.77/	Accepted insignificant and
TSL	0.13	Positive	/0.37/	Accepted insignificant and

Source: Computed.

Inference: Table 6 reveals that the correlation between the Combined Leverage and Earnings per Share for SAIL and TSL. It is observed that SAIL has positive correlation and TSL has negative correlation. The co-efficient determinations of SAIL and TSL are 0.2809 and 0.0169 respectively. That is 28.09% and 1.69% of variance in the combined leverage is accounted by earnings per share for both the companies. For t-test result, it is clear that the computed value is less than critical value for SAIL and TSL. Where, the null hypothesis is rejected for SAIL and accepted for TSL, but insignificant for both SAIL and TSL. Further, it is found that relationship between

financial leverage and earnings per share can be strong and negative relationship for SAIL. Whereas, TSL has weak and negative relationship at 5% level of significance.

Test of Significance (Using Market Price per Share)

Hypothesis 5.1(H₀): There is no significant difference between Operating Leverage and Market per Share.

Table 7 - Correlation and t-test result for Operating Leverage and Market Price per Share

Company	r ² value	Correlation result	t' value	Hypothesis result
SAIL	-0.40	Negative	/1.23/	Accepted insignificant and
TSL	0.053	Negative	/0.15/	Accepted insignificant and

Source: Computed.

Inference: Table 7, reveals the correlation between the Operating Leverage and Market Price per Share for SAIL has negative and TSL is having positive relation. The co-efficient determinations of SAIL and TSL are 0.16 and 0.00281 respectively. That is 16% and 0.28% of variance in the operating leverage is accounted by market price per share for each the company. For t-test result, it is clear that the computed value is lower than table value for both companies. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant relationship between operating leverage and market price per share for both the companies at 5% level of significance.

Hypothesis 2 (H₀): There is no significant difference between Financial Leverage and Market price per Share.

Table: 8

Correlation and t-test result for Financial Leverage and Market Price per Share

Company	r ² value	Correlation result	t' value	Hypothesis result
SAIL	-0.51	Negative	/1.68/	Accepted insignificant and
TSL	-0.17	Negative	/0.49/	Accepted insignificant and

Source: Computed.

Inference: Table 8 reveals the correlation between the Financial Leverage and Market Price per Share for SAIL and TSL is negative and weak relationship observed. The co-efficient determinations of SAIL and TSL are 0.2601 and 0.0289 respectively. That is 26.01% and 2.89% of variance in the financial leverage is accounted by market

price per share for each the company. For t-test result, it is clear that the computed value is lower than table value for both companies. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant relationship between financial leverage and market price per share for both the companies at 5% level of significance.

Hypothesis 5.3(H₀): There is no significant difference between Combined Leverage and Market per Share.

Table: 9 - Correlation and t-test result for Combined Leverage and Market Price per Share

Company	r value	Correlation result	t value	Hypothesis result
SAIL	0.52	Positive	/1.72/	Accepted and insignificant
TSL	-0.041	Negative	/0.12/	Accepted insignificant and

Source: Computed.

Inference: Table 9 reveals the correlation between the Combined Leverage and Market Price per Share for SAIL and TSL. SAIL has positive and TSL has negative correlation. The co-efficient determinations of SAIL and TSL are 0.2704 and 0.00168 respectively. That is 27.04% and 0.168% of variance in the combined leverage is accounted by market price per share for each the company. For t-test result, it is clear that the computed value is lower than Table value for both companies. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant relationship between combined leverage and market price per share for both the companies at 5% level of significance.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS:

This paper presents the main findings of the leverage and its impact on Earnings per Share and Market per Share of the SAIL and TSL over a period of ten years from 2003-2004 to 2012-2013. The following are the results of leverage and profitability performances of these two steel companies are observed.

Financial Leverages are concerned for both the companies; it is observed that TSL is favorable with operating leverage, financial leverage and combined leverages as compared to SAIL during the study period.

EPS and MPS are concerned, TSL has higher rate of earnings as compared to the SAIL. It implies that higher risk and more consistencies are considered by TSL, during the study period.

As result of the present study, we found strong support for the hypothesized relationship indicating that Financial Leverages with EPS and MPS for the above two steel companies.

It is observed that there is no significant difference between EPS and Financial leverages except operating leverage for SAIL. Further, it is concluded that financial leverage and combined leverages are correlated and operating leverage is uncorrelated with earnings per share for SAIL. All the result of hypothesis (H1) is supported by t-test statistically.

Finally, the result of this hypothesis (H2) and its sub hypotheses: It can be seen that there is no significant difference between MPS and three leverages statistically, which is supported by t-test. Further, it can be concluded that there exists correlation between Leverages and market price per share.

To conclude, our findings from the leverage, TSL is more favorable as compared to the SAIL and also better and progressive. It is suggested that SAIL has to improve its leverage. By the observed result from the study analysis and hypotheses, we knew that these two companies have wide scope to improve their profitability performance through leverage.

REFERENCES:

- Amasaveni, R (2009) 'Impact of Leverage on profitability Aluminium in India' Indian Journal of Finance. Volume3, Number 11, pp.33-41.
- Angales, L., (1995) what do we know about Capital Structure? Some evidence from international data. Journal of Finance 50, pp.1421-1460.
- Bhat and Ramesh (1980) determinants of financial leverage: Some further evidence, the chartered accounted December issue.
- Bhat, Ramesh Kumar (1980) Determinants of Financial Leverage: Some Further Evidence.
- David Durand (1952) "The cost of debt and equity funds for business". Management of corporate capital. The Free Press, New York
- Finance Management and policy -Bhalla, VK: Anol publications Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi - 110 002.
- Financial Management and policy: J.C Ven Horne; prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
- Financial Management and policy: J.C Ven Horne; prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
- Financial Management- Theory and practice - Prasanna Chandra; Tata Mc Graw Hill Company limited, New Delhi.
- Financial management- Weston and Birgham
- Financial Management; I.M. Pandey, Vikas Publishing House, Allahabad.
- Fundamentals of Financial management -James C. Van Horne; Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi